

IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF LICHEN RED PLANUS

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Abstract. The article is devoted to a detailed study of the immunohistochemical features of lichen planus, considering it at the cellular and molecular levels. The work uses immunohistochemical methods to analyze biopsy samples of skin affected by this disease. The authors of the article focus on identifying key immune markers involved in the development and progression of lichen planus by exploring the interaction between the immune system and skin cells

Keywords: Immunohistochemistry , Lichen planus, Immune markers

In connection with the aggravation of environmental problems and the increase in antigenic load on the human body, leading to structural and functional disorders, changes in the immune system in lichen planus (LP) of the oral mucosa are of particular interest. Thanks to modern research methods, it was possible to identify patterns of development of the lichenoid tissue reaction in LP, which is based on immune disorders characterized as delayed-type hypersensitivity. In this regard, correction of immunity is of particular importance [1, 6].

One of the approaches to immunotherapy for LP OB may include the use of exogenous interferons (Reaferon , Interlock) and interferonogens (Ridostin , Neovir). Considering the important role of the immunogenetic component in the pathogenesis of LP, it seems promising to develop a comprehensive treatment regimen for this disease including, along with traditional treatment methods, immunomodulators that increase the functional activity of the immune system. A promising and new group of immunomodulatory drugs are interferon inducers, which combine antibacterial, antiviral and immunocorrective properties [2].

In the last decade, in the pathogenesis of LP, researchers have paid special attention to the problem of the state of proliferative activity of epithelial cells. Using the immunohistochemical method, significant differences in the index of labeled nuclei in patients with LP were revealed and the connection between increased Ki-67 expression and disease progression was proven [5]. Proliferation processes are more pronounced in the epithelium of POPL lesions of the oral mucosa compared to the normal mucosa [7, 9, 10]. Changes in the

proliferative activity of the oral mucosa epithelium occur, among other things, in other dental diseases, as noted in numerous works by domestic and foreign authors [3, 4, 8].

Analyzing the literature data, we found isolated reports concerning the immunohistochemical characteristics of proliferating cells of the inflammatory infiltrate in LP OM. The study of the level of proliferative activity of epithelial cells in patients with LP of the oral mucosa was carried out without taking into account the severity of the inflammatory process [7, 9, 10]. We have not found data on determining the proliferative activity by the expression of the Ki-67 antigen in the epithelial cells of the buccal mucosa depending on the clinical form of LP of the oral mucosa in the domestic literature.

Purpose of the study: a comparative study of the proliferative activity of epithelial cells based on the expression of the Ki-67 antigen in patients with LP of the oral mucosa before and after treatment with the inclusion of an immunomodulator in complex therapy.

Material and research methods

An immunohistochemical study of biopsy samples of lesions of the buccal mucosa was carried out in 23 patients (10 men and 13 women - 43.5 and 56.5%, respectively) with clinical forms of LP of the oral mucosa: typical ($n = 12$) and erosive-ulcerative ($n = 11$) . The duration of the disease averaged 1.8 ± 0.44 years. As an immunomodulator, patients were prescribed the drug " Neovir " (sodium 10-methylene-carboxylate-9-acridine), which belongs to the group of low-molecular synthetic interferon inducers. The control group consisted of 15 practically healthy individuals without inflammatory lesions of the oral mucosa, of which 8 (53, 3%) men and 7 (46.7%) women.

The proliferative activity of cell populations in the buccal mucosa was assessed in the age group from 36 to 60 years (mature age, second period) using the immunohistochemical method (Ki-67 antigen), taking into account age-related changes in the oral mucosa.

Biopsies of the buccal mucosa measuring 2.0×2.0 mm were examined . In patients with LP, a fragment of the buccal mucosa was excised from lesions near the border of healthy tissue. The biopsy procedure was carried out under local anesthesia (2% lidocaine solution). To standardize the examination and exclude the influence of circadian rhythms on proliferation indicators, biopsy samples were taken from 9 to 11 o'clock [4]. Biopsies of the buccal mucosa of patients without pathological signs in the oral mucosa were used as a "healthy control" .

For immunohistochemical studies, samples were fixed for 24 hours in a 10% solution of neutral formaldehyde in phosphate buffer pH 7.5, and processed according to generally accepted methods and embedded in Histovac . Using a Lei microtome with a , serial sections with a thickness of 5-6 μm were made, which were mounted on glass slides treated with a 0.01% solution of poly-l-lysine (Poly -l- Lyzine solution 0.01%, Sigma USA). Antigen unmasking was carried out in a 10% Epitope solution Retrieval Solution pH 6 (NovocastaTM) at 95 °C in a water bath for 30 minutes.

Further immunohistochemical staining to detect Ki-67 positive cells was performed using the NovoLink kit (Polymer Detection System). RTU-Ki67-MM1 (NovocastaTM) was used as primary antibody . The final product of positively stained nuclei was visualized with 3,3-diaminobenzidine tetrachloride (DAB), and sections were counterstained with hematoxylin. As a result of treatment of the preparations, nuclei of proliferating cells were identified that were in the S-phase, in which maximum synthesis of Ki-67 is observed. The index of labeled nuclei, reflecting the level of expression of the Ki-67 antigen, was calculated in a Lei microscope with a at a magnification of 400. The index of labeled Ki-67 nuclei was determined after viewing at least 1500 nuclei of the regenerative zone and was expressed as a percentage.

Statistical processing of the results was carried out with the calculation of the average value and error of the average. The significance of differences was determined using Student's test. Differences were considered statistically significant if the achieved significance level (p) did not exceed the accepted critical significance level of 0.05.

Research results and discussion

In case of LP of the oral mucosa, before the start of treatment, disturbances in the processes of keratinization, proliferation and differentiation of epithelial cells were noted . The proliferative potential of epithelial cells of the oral mucosa, as judged by the expression of the Ki-67 antigen, differed qualitatively and quantitatively in patients in the control group (healthy individuals without pathological signs of inflammation of the buccal mucosa) and patients with LP of the oral mucosa. Analysis of the results revealed a significantly higher content of Ki-67-labeled cells in the epithelial layer from lesions of the buccal mucosa in patients with POPL of two forms (typical and erosive-ulcerative) compared with the control group. Individual differences in the cytoarchitecture and regenerative potential of oral mucosa erythelial cells were recorded . In the unchanged mucosa, positively stained Ki-67 nuclei were

detected only in the basal epithelial cells of the generative layer with a frequency of $15.48 \pm 0.41\%$. In patients with LP, the index of labeled cells was significantly 2.9 times higher and amounted to $45.0 \pm 1.0\%$ ($p < 0.05$). It should also be noted that there is a "blurring" or expansion of the boundaries of the proliferative pool of epithelial cells in patients with LP of the oral mucosa, that is, labeled cells were found in higher layers, in particular, in the spinous layer.

When comparing the typical and erosive-ulcerative forms of LP of the oral mucosa, significant differences in the index of labeled nuclei were established. The highest proliferative activity of epithelial cells in lesions of the buccal mucosa was found in patients with the erosive-ulcerative form ($50.66 \pm 1.34\%$), with the typical form of POPL, this figure was lower ($39.81 \pm 1.17\%$). The indices of labeled cells in erosive-ulcerative and typical forms of LP were higher, respectively, by 3.3 and 2.6 times ($p < 0.05$) than in the control group ($15.48 \pm 0.41\%$). The data obtained allow us to conclude that the frequency of detection of Ki-67 positively stained nuclei in the epithelium of the buccal mucosa is closely related to the clinical form of LP of the oral mucosa.

Comparative pathomorphological and immunohistochemical analysis of biopsy samples of the buccal mucosa of the same patients before and after traditional therapy using an immunomodulator revealed positive dynamics of morphological changes. This, first of all, concerned the number and size of infiltrates in the mucosa. Lymphocytic infiltration persisted mainly around small vessels; foci of free-lying infiltrates practically disappeared. The phenomena of acanthosis, hyperp- and parakeratosis also underwent significant regression. During treatment with traditional methods without the use of an immunomodulator, we did not observe a decrease in the severity of hyperkeratosis and parakeratosis; the granularity of the cytoplasm of cells in the upper parts of the spinous layer of the epithelium, as well as pronounced lymphocytic infiltration of the subepithelial zone, remained.

Analysis of changes in the index of Ki-67-labeled nuclei of epithelial cells revealed a pronounced tendency towards normalization of proliferative activity in patients who received an immunomodulator in addition to traditional therapy: the proliferation index decreased significantly (2 times) and amounted to $22.09 \pm 1.05\%$. The localization of Ki-67 positive cells also changed - labeled epithelial cells were located only in the first two rows from the basement membrane. The number of proliferating cells in the lamina propria of the mucous membrane also decreased. These data allow us to conclude that the use of the immunomodulator " Neovir " in the complex therapy of patients with LP of

the mucous membranes leads to a decrease in the severity of pathomorphological changes in the mucous membranes of the mucous membranes and a decrease in the proliferative activity of epithelial cells in the affected areas.

Conclusion

An immunohistochemical study of the proliferative activity of epithelial cells of the buccal mucosa revealed a significant increase in the percentage of Ki-67 positively stained nuclei in patients with POPL. Differences in the intensity of Ki-67 labeling of epithelial cell nuclei were established depending on the clinical form of LP of the oral mucosa: a higher level of Ki-67 expression in the epithelium of lesions of the buccal mucosa was detected in the erosive-ulcerative form of the disease.

The use of the immunomodulator " Neovir " in the complex therapy of patients with POPL leads to a decrease in the proliferative activity of epithelial cells and, as a consequence, a decrease in the severity of pathomorphological changes in the buccal mucosa.

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